

NOTES ON THE ORB-WEB SPIDER *ARANEUS APRICUS* (KARSCH, 1884) IN SOUTH AFRICA (ARANEAE: ARANEIDAE)

Anna S. Dippenaar-Schoeman^{1,2}, Stefan H. Foord² & Charles R. Haddad³

¹ ARC – Plant Health and Protection, Queenswood, South Africa

² Centre for Invasion Biology and Department of Zoology, University of Venda, Thohoyandou, South Africa

³ Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of the Free State, Bloemfontein, South Africa

Abstract: Data on the species diversity of *Araneus* (Araneidae) in South Africa is limited and outdated. A large number of Araneidae species were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa). *Araneus apricus* (Karsch, 1884), a species known from São Tomé, Yemen, Seychelles and Senegal, is also now recorded from South Africa. The presence of *A. apricus* in South Africa is discussed, with notes on their morphology based on live photographs, behaviour and distribution.

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) large numbers of specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). This includes many Araneidae specimens. Data on the current *Araneus* species diversity in South Africa is limited and outdated. For the first time, the green pea orb-web spider, *Araneus apricus* (Karsch, 1884), an African endemic species, was identified from South Africa. The species is known from the type locality, São Tomé, and has also been sampled in Yemen, Seychelles and Senegal (World Spider Catalog 2020).

The objective of this study is to discuss the behaviour, distribution and conservation status of *A. apricus* in South Africa, with notes on their morphology based on photographs of live specimens.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens examined are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA). As part of SANSa requests were made for photographs for the SANSa Virtual Museum and several were received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012).

TAXONOMY

Araneus apricus (Karsch, 1884)

Epeira aprica Karsch, 1884: 67, fig. 8 (Df).

Araneus apricus Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014.

Diagnostic characters: Size: TL females 8–7 mm, males slightly smaller and with darker markings. *Araneus apricus* can be easily recognised by their distinct body shape and green abdomen. Carapace shiny, blackish brown (Figs 1-3); cephalic region raised, bearing scattered white setae (Fig. 5). Eyes in two rows; lateral eyes situated close together near carapace edge; anterior median eyes largest, well separated; posterior median eyes closer together (Fig. 2). Sternum brown, heart-shaped, bearing scattered long white setae (Fig. 4). Abdomen round, partly overlapping the carapace; shoulder humps not distinct; integument bearing short white setae (Fig. 5); dark

patch present on anterior edge, sometimes stretching on both sides to half abdomen length; area around patch sometimes with yellow tint (Fig. 5); abdomen pale brown ventrally, with yellow spots on both sides of epigynum (Fig. 4). Legs paler than carapace, varying from brown with distinct bands on femora and tibiae (Figs 2-4) to brown without bands (Fig. 5). Epigyne with long scape (Fig. 8). Male unknown.

Behaviour: They build their orb-webs at night (Fig. 7) and remove them in the early morning. They spend the day in a retreat composed of a cluster of leaves pulled together with silk threads (Fig. 6). The cryptic colouration of the abdomen helps to camouflage them. Field observations showed that the species is much more abundant in the summer months. They appear to be largely restricted to the shrub and tree layer, between 1.5 and 2 m above ground level.

Medical importance: This species is one of the few araneids for which a case study on their bite symptoms exists (Haddad 2002). The bite was not especially painful, local swelling and red dermal colouration around the bite site developed, with the thumb and forefinger area becoming numb. Within the first hour sharp pain developed in the bicep, armpit, shoulder, lateral chest and pectoral muscles, after which discomfort levels decreased. Lymph glands in the armpit also started to swell during this time. Intense pain began developing in the thumb and index finger an hour after envenomation, and continued during the subsequent hours. Local swelling around the bite site gradually increased to an area approximately 2.5 cm in diameter, which was bright red in colour and extremely itchy. Swelling of the hand and armpit glands receded within 8 hours of the bite. A small scar formed at the site of the bite marks, which healed after 16 days (without any treatment), and no tissue necrosis occurred.

Habitat: They have been sampled from several of the floral biomes in South Africa, such as the Savanna (Foord *et al.* 2011), Grassland (Haddad *et al.* 2013), as well as the Fynbos, Forest and Nama Karoo biomes. The species were also found in agroecosystems such as avocado, citrus and macadamia orchards and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2013).

Figure 1–9. *Araneus apricus* (Karsch, 1884) females from South Africa. (1) Dorsal view; (2) Anterior view, showing eye pattern and band on abdomen; (3) Dorsolateral view, showing the carapace shape; (4) Ventral view; (5) Dorsal view, showing colour variation; (6) Female in retreat; (7) Female in orb-web; (8) Epigyne, ventral view; (9) Map showing the known distribution of *Araneus apricus* (Karsch, 1884) in South Africa. Photos (except 8, A.D.S.): Peter Webb.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park (-33.343, 25.739), leg. L. Wiese, 1 f (NCA 2011/1289); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (Ferndale Farm, Keurkloof) (-33.656, 24.541), leg. M. le Roux, 1f (NCA 2009/3133); Coffee Bay (-31.981, 29.152), leg. C. Haddad & R. Lyle, beating, 1f (NCA 2007/393). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77), leg. R. Lyle, 2f (NCA 2005/1391); Same locality, leg. A. Leroy, 2f (NCA 2005/1391); Pretoria (-25.74, 28.19), leg. S. Nesar, 1f (NCA 91/164); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36), leg. M. Stiller, 13.xi.1980, 1f (NCA 92/244); Wonderboom Nature Reserve (-25.69, 28.19), leg. A. Dippenaar, 1.ii.1981, 1f (NCA 81/647). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), leg. S. Lovell, 1f (NCA 2004/156); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), leg. P. Reavell, 6.x.1977, 1imm. f (NCA 78/177); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24), leg. C. Haddad, 1f (NCA 2011/1289); Pongola, Farm Vergeval (-27.35, 31.61), leg. A. Dippenaar, 2.vi.1967, 1imm. f (NCA 77/1016); Tembe Elephant Park (-

26.94, 32.47), leg. C. Haddad, 1f (NCA 2008/1598); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.20), leg. J. Leroy, 1f (NCA 2009/5393). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93), leg. B. Grobbelaar, 18.i.1991, 1f (NCA 91/89); Kruger National Park, Pafuri (-22.93, 31.06), leg. J. Braack, 18.iii.1974, 1f (NCA 91/1660); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.162, 30.254), leg. P. Webb, 3.ii.2015, 5f (NCA 2015/3500); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45), leg. R. Lyle & R. Fourie, 1f (NCA 2008/484); Letaba (-23.82, 30.16), leg. C.J. Cilliers, 12.xii.1979, 1f (NCA 81/556); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.70), leg. A. Leroy, 4.iv.1980, 3f (NCA 81/146); Nylstroom/ Modimolle (-24.69, 28.40), leg. A. Honiball, sweeping, 1f (NCA 2008/791); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67), leg. G. Ferreira, 7.iii.1976, 1f (NCA 78/473); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47), leg. T. Khoza & M. Modiba, sweeping, 1f (NCA 2008/2136); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63), leg. M. Filmer, 3.iv.1986, 1f (NCA 87/138); Sandringham Nature Reserve (-24.58, 31.10), leg. N. Dippenaar, 7.iv.1974, 1f (NCA 76/835); Soutpansberg, Farm Little Leigh (-

22.95, 29.87), leg. N. Hahn, 1f (NCA 2009/1996). **Mpumalanga:** Badplaas (-25.95, 30.56), leg. J. van As, 1m (NCA 2005/337); Brondal (-25.35, 30.84), leg. M van den Berg, 7.iv.1998, avocado, 1f (NCA 98/1006); Burgers Hall (-25.08, 31.08), leg. M. van den Berg, citrus, 2f (NCA 2009/649); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23), leg. A. Dippenaar, 6.iv.1974, 1f (NCA 76/1816); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00), leg. A. Leroy, 1f (NCA 2008/2675); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96), leg. M van den Berg, fogging macadamia trees, 1f (NCA 98/789). **Northern Cape:** Hopetown, Farm Suffolk (-29.58, 24.24), leg. R. Lyle & R. Fourie, 1f (NCA 2010/771); Rooipoort Nature Reserve, leg. R. Lyle & P. Lyle, 22.iii.2013, 1f (NCA 2015/4242). **North West:** Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82), leg. M. Filmer, 26.iii.1989, 1f (NCA 89/912); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85), leg. A. Capener, 10.iii.1966, 1imm. f (NCA 77/1019); Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32), leg. M. Filmer, 15.iii.1978, 1f (NCA 87/472); Magaliesburg (-25.99, 27.54), leg. M. Filmer, 3.iii.1987, 1m (NCA 87/692); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18), leg. M. Stiller, 30.iv.1981, 1f (NCA 84/288). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44), leg. C. Haddad, 1f (NCA 2007/3855); Jonkershoek Nature Reserve (-33.98, 18.98), leg. E. Pietersen, 1f (NCA 2010/3293); Outeniqua Nature Reserve (-33.92, 22.43), leg. D. Damon, 1f (NCA 2010/2402).

Global distribution: An African endemic species that was described from São Tomé and has been collected from four African countries (São Tomé, Yemen [mainland Socotra], Seychelles and South Africa). This species is possibly undercollected and suspected to occur in more countries in-between. In South Africa it is fairly common and has been collected from eight provinces (Fig. 9).

Conservation status: The species receives protection in several protected areas such as: Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2009), Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 1989), Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.* 2008), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.* 2006), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.* 2009), Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.* 2016) and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009). Due to the species' wide range, and the absence of threats to its survival, it is listed according to the IUCN criteria as Least Concern.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was made possible through financial support from the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the National Research Foundation of South Africa. Authors want to thank Peter Webb for sharing his photographs.

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2014. *Field Guide of the Spiders of South Africa*. Lapa Publishers, 424 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H., LYLE, R., LOTZ, L.N. & MARAIS, P. 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSAN): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae), *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 70: 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., LYLE, R. & VAN DEN BERG, A.M. 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* 13: 121–127.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., VAN DEN BERG, A. & PRENDINI, L. 2009. A checklist of spiders and scorpions of the Nylsvley Nature Reserve, South Africa. *Koedoe* 50: 1–9.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., VAN DEN BERG, A.M., HADDAD, C.R. & LYLE, R. 2013. Spiders in South African agroecosystems: a review (Arachnida, Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 57–74.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., VAN DEN BERG, A.M. & VAN DEN BERG, A. 1989. Species composition and relative seasonal abundance of spiders from the field and tree layers of the Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve. *Koedoe* 32: 51–60.
- FOORD, S.H., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & HADDAD, C.R. 2011. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Savanna Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 66: 170–201.
- FOORD, S.H., MAFADZA, M., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & VAN RENSBURG, B.J. 2008. Micro-scale heterogeneity of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) in the Soutpansberg, South Africa: a comparative survey and inventory in representative habitats. *African Zoology* 43: 156–174.
- HADDAD, C.R. 2002. Symptoms of the bite of an orb-web spider *Araneus apricus* (Araneae: Araneidae). *South African Medical Journal* 92: 528–529.
- HADDAD, C.R. & DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. 2009. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the De Hoop Nature Reserve, Western Cape Province, South Africa. *Koedoe* 51(#149): 1–9.
- HADDAD, C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., FOORD, S.H., LOTZ, L.N. & LYLE, R. 2013. The faunistic diversity of spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Grassland Biome in South Africa. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* 68: 97–122.
- HADDAD, C.R., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S. & WESOŁOWSKA, W. 2006. A checklist of the non-acarine arachnids (Chelicerata: Arachnida) of the Ndumo Game Reserve, Maputaland, South Africa. *Koedoe* 49: 1–22.
- HADDAD, C.R., HONIBALL, A., DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., JANSE VAN RENSBURG, B.J. & SLOTOW, R. 2009. Spiders as potential indicators of elephant-induced habitat changes in endemic sand forest, Maputaland, South Africa. *African Journal of Ecology* 48: 446–460.
- KARSCH, F. 1884. Arachnoidea. In: Greeff, R. (ed.) *Die Fauna der Guinea-Inseln S.-Thomé und Rolas. Sitzungsberichte der Gesellschaft zur Beförderung der Gesamten Naturwissenschaften zu Marburg* 2: 60–68, 79.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG 2020. World Spider Catalog, version 19.5. Natural History Museum Bern. Online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch> [accessed 8 October 2020].